

ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY AND REGIONAL DIFFERENCES IN MILK PRODUCTION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF KALYANA KARNATAKA AND THE REST OF KARNATAKA

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Abstract

This study evaluates the economic efficiency of milk production in two distinct regions of Karnataka - Kalyana Karnataka (represented by Koppal district) and the rest of Karnataka (represented by Ramanagara district). Using data from 120 dairy farmers collected during the 2024-25 agricultural year, the research highlights regional differences in livestock composition, resource management and cooperative support. Ramanagara, with a predominance of crossbred cows and stronger cooperative infrastructure, showed higher profitability, better cost control and greater returns per investment compared to Koppal, where buffaloes are more common. The average total cost per animal per day was ₹ 140.39 in Ramanagara and ₹ 128.02 in Koppal, but Ramanagara's net returns (₹ 32.53) were more than double those of Koppal (₹ 15.11). Additionally, Ramanagara recorded a lower cost per litre of milk, indicating more efficient production. These findings confirm the influence of agro-climatic and socio-economic factors on dairy production efficiency. The study emphasizes the need for strengthening dairy cooperatives and implementing region-specific incentive policies to improve productivity and profitability in lagging areas. This research offers valuable insights for policymakers aiming to promote balanced and sustainable dairy development across Karnataka.

Keywords : Milk production, Economic efficiency, Regional differences, Dairy cooperatives, Karnataka, Cost and returns.

Introduction

India's dairy sector stands as a cornerstone of rural livelihoods, food security and economic resilience, showing sustained growth even during crises like COVID-19. Contributing 5.5 per cent to national GDP and over 30 per cent to agricultural GDP (Anonymous, 2023), livestock particularly dairying provides income, nutrition and employment to millions of small and marginal farmers, including landless labourers. As the world's largest milk producer, with an output of 239.2 million tonnes in 2023-24, India's dairy industry has transformed, driven by rising incomes, urbanization and changing dietary preferences that have shifted agriculture towards high-value commodities.

Despite this progress, the sector faces challenges. Productivity is hindered by inadequate breeding services, poor feed and nutrition and limited veterinary care, even as crop-livestock interdependence remains vital to rural economies. The 20th Livestock Census (2019) reported a 4.6 per cent increase in livestock numbers to 535.78 million, with notable growth shifts towards eastern and southern regions (Anonymous, 2019). Milk consumption has strengthened, raising per capita availability to 471 grams per day in India above the global average but still below ICAR's recommended level for optimal nutrition.

The transformation of India's dairy landscape owes much to the White Revolution and adoption of the Anand-type cooperative model, exemplified by the Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers' Federation (KMF). Building on Operation Flood, KMF established a strong three-tier cooperative network comprising over 15,000 Dairy Cooperative Societies, 15 milk unions and infrastructure for procurement, processing, chilling and feed production. This framework ensures fair prices for farmers and provides quality products to consumers, empowering rural communities across Karnataka (KMF, 2022-23).

Given the crucial role of dairy cooperatives in boosting rural incomes, there is a need to analyze the cost and returns of milk production in Kalyana Karnataka and the rest of Karnataka to identify disparities, improve efficiency and ensure sustainable growth of the dairy economy. The study was undertaken with the specific objective to estimate the costs, returns of milk production in the study area.

Material and Methods

A multistage stratified random sampling method was adopted in selection of sample respondents. First, two milk unions- RBKMUL from Kalyana Karnataka and BAMUL from the rest of Karnataka were selected again from these, Koppal and Ramanagara districts were chosen. Second, from selected district two taluks and three MPCs from

each taluk; finally, ten dairy farmers were randomly selected. Thus total 120 respondent farmers selected for the study.

The data pertained to the agricultural year 2024-25. The primary data was collected with the help of a well-designed, pre-tested and comprehensive schedule exclusively prepared for the purpose. The schedule was prepared after discussing with various specialists.

The costs and returns of milk production in the study area were estimated and analyzed using tabular analysis.

Estimation of Cost of milk production

It is important to study the cost of milk production as it is an indicator of economic efficiency of milk production and indicates the profitability of the enterprise. The various cost components were identified as fixed cost and variable cost. These costs are discussed briefly in this section.

Fixed costs: Fixed costs relate to those costs, which remain unchanged over the short time period. Fixed costs includes depreciation on fixed assets like animals, cattle shed, interest on fixed capital & insurance premium, if any.

Variable costs: Variable costs include labour charges, feed and feeding stuffs, maintenance, miscellaneous expenses, etc.

Amortization cost of farm buildings/dairy shed

The capital cost of the farm buildings/dairy shed was allocated as equal yearly instalments throughout the economic life of the farm buildings/shed. In order to estimate the annual share of the farm buildings/shed, the following formula is adopted

$$\text{Amortization cost (A)} = P \times r (1+r)^n / (1+r)^n - 1 \quad \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where,

A = Annual amortization cost (₹)

P = Investment cost of farm buildings/dairy shed (₹)

r = Discount rate (9 % per annum)

n = Economic life of buildings/dairy shed in years (20 years)

Result and Discussion

Type and distribution of dairy animals among sample respondents (Table 1) reflected significant variation across the study areas. In Ramanagara, local cows constituted 32 animals (15.69 %) while Koppal had a higher number with 42 animals (22.22 %). Crossbred cows dominated both areas with 112 animals (54.90 %) in Ramanagara and 72 animals (38.10 %) in Koppal. Buffaloes also represented a substantial share, with 60 animals (29.41 %) in Ramanagara and 75 animals (39.68 %) in Koppal. On average, farmers owned about 3.4 animals in Ramanagara and 3.15 animals in Koppal. The results reflect regional disparities in Karnataka's dairy sector, with more crossbred cows in southern Ramanagara and buffaloes in northern Koppal,

influenced by agro-climatic and socio-economic factors. The results align with Somasekaran *et al.* (2025).

The cost and returns of milk production per animal per day in the study areas reveal clear disparities between Ramanagara and Koppal, reflecting differences in economic viability and efficiency. The total fixed cost in Ramanagara was ₹ 52.90, slightly higher by ₹ 3.05 than ₹ 49.85 in Koppal, constituting 59.73 % and 60.71 % of the total cost, respectively. Variable costs, mainly feed-related, were ₹ 87.49 in Ramanagara, surpassing Koppal's ₹ 78.17 by ₹ 9.32, and contributing to a higher total cost of ₹ 140.39 per animal per day compared to ₹ 128.02 in Koppal (Table 4.2). Returns from milk production further emphasized these disparities, with Ramanagara recording ₹ 155.62 per animal per day, which was ₹ 31.25 higher than Koppal's ₹ 124.37. This resulted in a net return of ₹ 32.53 in Ramanagara, more than double Koppal's ₹ 15.11, underscoring the greater profitability in the former. Gross returns were also substantially higher in Ramanagara at ₹ 172.92, compared to ₹ 143.13 in Koppal, with an average gross return of ₹ 158.03 in the combined study area. Returns per rupee of investment highlight the efficiency gap, being 0.23 in Ramanagara versus 0.12 in Koppal, indicating more effective resource utilization. Moreover, the cost per litre of milk was ₹ 28.19 in Ramanagara, lower than Koppal's ₹ 32.17, reflecting better cost control. These disparities point to the influence of factors such as resource management, cooperative support and operational efficiency favoring Ramanagara, which aligns with the observations of Choudhary and Singh (2023).

The financial performance of dairy farming per animal per day in Ramanagara and Koppal, as presented in Table 4.3, reveals comparatively higher profitability in Ramanagara. Net returns over total fixed cost were ₹ 120.02 in Ramanagara against ₹ 93.28 in Koppal, while net returns over total variable cost were ₹ 85.43 and ₹ 64.96, respectively. Similarly, net returns over total cost accounted for ₹ 32.53 in Ramanagara compared to ₹ 15.11 in Koppal, thereby confirming the relatively better economic viability of dairy farming in the former. These disparities are also observed in cost structures, with Ramanagara incurring a slightly higher total fixed cost (₹ 52.90 vs ₹ 49.85) and notably higher total variable cost (₹ 87.49 vs ₹ 78.17), resulting in a total cost difference of ₹ 12.37 per animal per day. Despite these higher costs, Ramanagara's gross return exceeded Koppal's by ₹ 29.79 (₹ 172.92 vs ₹ 143.13), reflecting more efficient resource utilization and economic performance. Further, milk returns improved substantially with the implementation of the Milk Producers' Incentive Scheme (MPI

sheme). In Ramanagara, net returns from milk increased from ₹ 155.62 (without MPI sheme) to ₹ 180.52 (with MPI sheme), whereas in Koppal, they enhanced from ₹ 124.37 to ₹ 144.27. This incremental gain of ₹ 36.25 in Ramanagara compared to ₹ 19.90 in Koppal emphasizes the crucial role of cooperative interventions and incentive programs in augmenting dairy farmers' incomes while maintaining the revenue gap. These observations corroborate the findings of Rohith *et al.* (2019), who reported substantial improvements in dairy farm profitability and efficiency due scheme implementation. The relatively higher financial gains observed in Ramanagara may be attributed to efficient resource utilization and stronger cooperative support, thereby underlining the importance of institutional arrangements in safeguarding farmer livelihoods and fostering dairy sector growth in the region.

The financial performance of dairy farming per farmer per day in Ramanagara and Koppal, as detailed in Table 4.4, indicates a clear disparity in profitability favoring Ramanagara. The total fixed cost incurred was ₹ 179.86 in Ramanagara, which was higher by ₹ 22.83 compared to ₹ 157.03 in Koppal. Similarly, the total variable cost was substantially higher in Ramanagara at ₹ 297.47 versus ₹ 246.24 in Koppal, resulting in a notable total cost difference of ₹ 74.06 per farmer per day. Despite the higher costs, Ramanagara's gross return markedly exceeded that of Koppal by ₹ 137.07, standing at ₹ 587.93 compared to ₹ 450.86. This resulted in higher net returns over total fixed cost of ₹ 408.07 in Ramanagara against ₹ 293.83 in Koppal, and net returns over total variable cost of ₹ 290.46 versus ₹ 204.62. The net returns over total cost also reflected significant gains, with Ramanagara achieving ₹ 110.60, more than double the ₹ 47.60 recorded in Koppal, reaffirming the superior economic viability of dairy farming per farmer in Ramanagara. Further, net returns from milk without the Milk Producers' Incentive Scheme (MPIS) were ₹ 529.11 in Ramanagara compared to ₹ 391.77 in Koppal, a difference of ₹ 137.34. With the inclusion of MPIS, net returns improved substantially reaching ₹ 613.77 in Ramanagara and ₹ 454.45 in Koppal, widening the gap to ₹ 159.32. This demonstrates the important contribution of incentive schemes in enhancing the income of dairy farmers, while also highlighting the more effective cooperative structure and resource management in Ramanagara relative to Koppal. These results corroborated the findings of Rohith *et al.* (2019), who reported substantial improvements in dairy farm profitability and efficiency due scheme implementation.

Table 1: Type and distribution of dairy animals among sample respondent farmers in study area

Sl. No.	Type of animal	Ramanagara (n ₁ =60)		Koppal (n ₂ =60)	
		Animals (No.)	%	Animals (No.)	%
1	Local cow	32	15.69	42	22.22
2	Crossbred cow	112	54.90	72	38.10
3	Buffalo	60	29.41	75	39.68
Total		204	-	189	-
Average number of milk animals per farmer		3.4	-	3.15	-

Table 2: Cost and returns of milk production in the study area during 2024-25

(₹/animal/day)

Sl. No.	Particulars	Ramanagara (n ₁ =60)			Koppal (n ₂ =60)		
		Qty.	Value(₹)	%	Qty.	Value(₹)	%
A	Fixed cost						
1	Amortized cost of farm buildings/shed	-	21.41	15.25	-	19.43	15.18
2	Amortized cost of animal	-	17.21	32.53	-	16.26	32.62
3	Interest on investment @ 9%	-	12.77	9.10	-	12.65	9.88
4	Animal insurance	-	1.51	2.85	-	1.51	3.03
	Total fixed cost	-	52.9	59.73	-	49.85	60.71
B	Variable cost						
1	Green fodder (Kg.)	18	18.21	12.97	16	16.84	13.15
2	Dry fodder (Kg.)	6	11.31	8.06	5	9.14	7.14
3	Concentrates (Kg.)	2.5	20.1	14.32	2	19.74	15.42
	Total feed cost	-	49.62	35.34	-	45.72	35.71
4	Imputed family labour	-	13.74	9.79	-	12.35	9.65
5	Hired labour	-	16.95	12.07	-	14.62	11.42
6	Medical expenses	-	1.88	1.34	-	1.61	1.26
7	Miscellaneous expenses	-	5.3	3.78	-	3.87	3.02
	Total variable cost	-	87.49	62.32	-	78.17	61.06
	Total cost (A+B)		140.39	-	-	128.02	-
C	Returns						
1	Return from milk	4.98	155.62	90.00	3.98	124.37	86.89
2	Return from by sale of dung	-	17.3	10.00	-	18.76	13.11
	Gross return	-	172.92	100.00	-	143.13	100.00
	Net return	-	32.53	-	-	15.11	-
	Returns per rupee of investment	-	0.23	-	-	0.12	-
	Cost per liter of milk	-	28.19	-	-	32.17	-

Table 4.3: Financial performance of dairy farming per animal per day in study area

(₹/animal/day)

Sl. No.	Category	Ramanagara (n ₁ =60)	Koppal (n ₂ =60)	Difference
1	Total fixed cost	52.90	49.85	3.05
2	Total variable cost	87.49	78.17	9.32
3	Total cost	140.39	128.02	12.37
4	Gross return	172.92	143.13	29.79
5	Net returns over total fixed cost	120.02	93.28	26.74
6	Net returns over total variable cost	85.43	64.96	20.47
7	Net returns over total cost	32.53	15.11	17.42
8	Net return from the milk without Milk Producers' Incentive Scheme	155.62	124.37	31.25
9	Net return from the milk with Milk Producers' Incentive Scheme	180.52	144.27	36.25

Table 4.4: Financial performance of dairy farming per farmer per day in study area

(₹/farmer/day)

Sl. No.	Category	Ramanagara (n ₁ =60)	Koppal (n ₂ =60)	Difference
1	Total fixed cost	179.86	157.03	22.83
2	Total variable cost	297.47	246.24	51.23
3	Total cost	477.33	403.26	74.06
4	Gross return	587.93	450.86	137.07
5	Net returns over total fixed cost	408.07	293.83	114.24
6	Net returns over total variable cost	290.46	204.62	85.84
7	Net returns over total cost	110.60	47.60	63.01
8	Net return from the milk without Milk Producers' Incentive Scheme	529.11	391.77	137.34
9	Net return from the milk with Milk Producers' Incentive Scheme	613.77	454.45	159.32

Conclusion

The analysis reveals significant regional disparities in dairy production between Ramanagara and Koppal. Ramanagara demonstrates higher profitability, better cost efficiency, and greater returns per investment, likely due to superior resource management and cooperative support. These findings underscore the importance of strengthening dairy cooperatives and incentive schemes to enhance economic viability and productivity in less efficient regions like Koppal, supporting balanced growth across Karnataka's dairy sector.

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